

STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY ASSESSMENT OF A DISTRESSED BUILDING IN UNWANA USING NON DESTRUCTIVE TESTING

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Abstract

The study investigated the structural integrity of a distressed building located at Unwana Afikpo., Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Visual inspection was conducted and visible cracks were identified on walls and columns of the distressed building. Geotechnical investigations such as Dynamic Cone Penetration Test (DCPT) and laboratory tests were conducted on the disturbed soil samples at 0.37m and 0.90m depth to evaluate the soil properties. Also, Non Destructive Test (NDT) technique using Schmidt hammer apparatus was used to test the grade of the hardened concrete of the distressed building. The results obtained from the laboratory tests conducted for the soil samples revealed that at 0.37m depth, the plastic Limit (PL), Liquid Limit (LL) and Plasticity Index (PI) of the disturbed sample collected were 6.2%, 16.1%, 9.9% respectively and based on USCS and AASHTO soil classification, the soil was GC (clayey gravel) and A-2-4 (silty or clayey gravel) as $PI > 7$ and $LL < 40$. The result of PL, LL and PI at 0.9m depth for the disturbed soil sample was found as 34.2%, 52.2%, and 18% respectively and based on USCS and AASHTO soil classification, the soil was MH (inorganic silt) and A-7-5 (clayey soil) as $PI < 30$ and $LL > 50$. DCP test result revealed that the soil was clayey soil with low bearing capacity of 53KN/m^2 . The soil characteristics indicated that the soil will be problematic for construction due to clayey contents and has tendency to undergo volume changes with moisture fluctuations. The NDT result gave an average compressive strength of 20N/mm^2 indicating that the grade of concrete was fair for the distressed building. The Investigations showed that the strip foundation and column base at 0.37m and 0.9m depth respectively were not adequate to withstand the design loads of the building due to the clayey nature of the soil. It was recommended that the soil should be treated and foundation repairs provided to improve the life span of the building and prevent possible collapse that may lead to loss of lives and properties.

Keywords: Distressed Building, Structural Integrity Assessment. Non Destructive Test (NDT) and Dynamic Cone Penetration Test (DCPT), Geotechnical investigation

Introduction

Structural assessment is a vital process used to evaluate the safety, stability, and performance of an existing structure that show signs of distress or damage (Akali et. al, 2018; Sinha & Agarwal, 2012). The distress in buildings can result from structural deterioration, overloading, climatic conditions such as temperature fluctuations, moisture ingress and construction deficiencies (Eze et. al 2023; Mohd, 2022; Hine, 2013; Zerva & Dritsos, 2014). These distresses in building pose the potential risks for partial or complete structural failure, which can lead to loss of life, injury, or properties. Thus, it is essential to perform a comprehensive structural assessment to identify these issues early and determine the best method to adopt to provide solutions (Harris, 2010). The methods of structural assessment commonly used include visual inspection to detect visible signs of distressed such as cracks and other material degradation; Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) methods such as Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Test and Schmidt Rebound Hammer Test; and Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) that employs the use of sensors and advanced data analytics to continuously monitor the health of a building over time (Anand et. al, 2021; Kumar.& Sharmila ,2023; Morrow & Schmid, 2018). The attempt to investigate the structural integrity of buildings particularly in Nigeria has increased tremendously due to the high rate of building collapse in the country. Ibrahim et al, (2020), carried out structural integrity assessment of a two storey school building in Gumel, Jigawa State using NDT method. Similar investigations were carried out by Akali et al, 2018, Muhammad et al., 2021, Sule et al., 2023, Eze et al., 2023 and Ojedele et.al 2024. These investigations addressed assessments of buildings in Maiduguri, Abuja Enugu, and Ibadan. Presently, most structures in Unwana, Afikpo-North local government area of Ebonyi state were constructed without conducting cube tests to determine the grade of concrete structural elements. Also, geotechnical investigations were not conducted to ascertain the bearing capacity of the soil. The study tends to investigate the structural integrity of a residential distressed building within the study region.

Methods

The following techniques were used to access the structural integrity of the distressed building under investigation; Visual Inspection, Geotechnical Investigation, Non-Destructive Test.

Visual Inspection

Visual inspection was carried out on the distressed building behind Oga Boss Restaurant and Bar located at Unwana in Afikpo, Ebonyi State Nigeria and lies within coordinate 5°47'45"N latitude and 7°56'13"E longitude as shown in figure 1. Figure 2 showed signs of visible cracks identified on the walls and other structural elements of the distressed building. This led to further investigation to access the structural integrity of the distressed building to determine its reliability to carry existing loads and future loads.

Figure 1: Map showing location of Site at Unwana, Afikpo.
Source: Google map

Figure 2: visible cracks in the distressed building

Geotechnical Investigation

A geotechnical investigation was conducted to evaluate the soil conditions beneath the building foundation. A total of two (2) disturbed soil samples were collected manually from areas with severe cracks at 0.37m and 0.9m depth respectively and transported to the laboratory to investigate the engineering properties of the soil surrounding the distressed building in accordance to BS 1377. The tests conducted were particle size analysis, moisture content determination test and Atterberg Limit Tests. Dynamic Cone Penetration Test (DCPT), a field test was also carried out at different foundation depths of the excavated points to determine the bearing capacity of the soil as shown in figure 3..

Figure 3: Dynamic Cone Penetration Test (DCPT) on the distressed building

Non Destructive Test (NDT)

Non-destructive test (NDT) using Schmidt rebound hammer apparatus was used to measure the surface hardness and estimate the compressive strength of the hardened concrete of the structural elements of the distressed building in accordance with ASTM C805/C05M. The values of the compressive strength of concrete for the distressed building were interpreted as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Average Rebound Rating for Concrete

Average Rebound Numbers	Quality of Concrete
> 40	Very Good
30 to 40	Good
20 to 30	Fair
< 20	Poor
0	Delaminated

Source: Ojedele et al. (2024)

Results and Discussions

Particle Size Analysis Results

Table 2a: Particle Size Analysis Results for 0.37m Depth

Sieve Analysis Results at 0.37m Depth					
Sieve Number	Sieve Diameter (mm)	Weight Retained (g)	% Weight Retained	Cumulative % Weight Retained	Fine % Passing
4	4.75	185.7	37.17	37.17	62.83
10	2	178	35.63	72.8	27.2
20	0.85	84	16.81	89.61	10.39
40	0.425	27	5.41	95.02	4.98
80	0.212	10.3	2.06	97.08	2.92
100	0.15	2	0.4	97.48	2.52
200	0.075	1.2	0.24	97.72	2.28
Pan	-	12.6	2.52	100	0
		Summation = 499.6			

Figure 4: Particle Size Analysis Graph at 0.37m Depth

Table 2b: Particle Size Analysis Results for 0.9m Depth

Sieve Analysis Results for 0.90m Depth					
Sieve Number	Sieve Diameter (mm)	Weight Retained (g)	% Weight Retained	Cumulative % Weight Retained	Fine or Passing
4	4.75	82.9	16.74	16.74	83.26
10	2	158.3	31.96	48.7	51.3
20	0.85	156.4	31.57	80.27	19.75
40	0.425	58	11.71	91.98	8.02
80	0.212	20	4.04	96.02	3.98
100	0.15	4.5	0.91	96.93	3.07
200	0.075	2.4	0.48	97.42	2.58
Pan	-	15.2	3.07	100	0
		Summation = 495.3			

Figure 5: Particle Size Analysis Graph at 0.90m Depth

The results of the sieve analysis tests for the disturbed samples collected at depth 0.37m and 0.9m of the distressed building were presented in tables' 2a-b and figures 4-5 respectively. The coefficient of curvature (Cc) and coefficient of uniformity (Cu) for the disturbed sample at 0.37m depth were 0.68 and 5.25 respectively indicating that the soil was poorly graded as (Cc) value was not within 1-3 and (Cu) was less than 6 based on Unified Soil Classification System (USCS). Also, the Cc and Cu values at 0.9m depth were 0.56 and 5.41 respectively revealing that the soil was poorly graded.

Moisture Content Determination Test Result

The result of the moisture content determination test for the disturbed sample was presented in table 3. The moisture content at 0.37m depth was found to be 24.83% indicating moderately wet soil, which might be near its optimum moisture content, which is important for compaction and was classified according to AASTHO to be fine grained soil (silty or clayey soil) that can retain significant water. Also, the moisture content at 0.90m depth was found to be 31.82% indicating that the soil had wetter conditions at a deeper depth which may reduce the shear strength and bearing capacity of the soil. The high moisture contents might suggest problematic soils for foundations.

Table 3: Moisture Content Laboratory Test Results.

Laboratory Test Result				
	Sample 1 (0.37m)		Sample 2 (0.90m)	
Container number	A3	D	B5	S
Weight of Empty Container W_1	50	50	46.6	49.2
Weight of Container + Wet sample (gram) W_2	74.4	74.7	63.9	67.1
Weight of Container + Dry sample (gram) W_3	68.9	68	58.4	61.9
weight of Wet Sample only (gram)	24.4	24.7	17.3	17.9
Weight of Dry sample only (gram)	5.5	6.7	5.5	5.7
Weight of Water	18.9	18	11.8	12.2
Moisture Content	22.54	27.13	31.79	31.84
Average Moisture Content	24.84		31.82	

Atterberg Limit Test Results

Table 4a: Atterberg Limit Test Result at 0.37m depth

Depth:	0.37m					
Atterberg Limit Test Results						
	Liquid Limit (LL)				Plastic Limit (PL)	
Number of blows	35	37	21	14		
Can number	G4	G5	H1	A1	B1	B2
Can weight (g)	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5
Can weight + wet soil (g)	17.7	18	19.5	18.1	14.56	14.1
Can weight + dry soil (g)	16.9	16.8	18	16.7	14.3	13.8
Weight of water (g) (A)	0.8	1.2	1.5	1.4	0.26	0.3
Weight of dry soil (g) (B)	7.4	7.3	8.5	7.2	4.8	4.3
Moisture content % (A/B * 100)	10.8	16.4	17.6	19.4	5.4	6.9
AASHTO Classification	A-2-4					
USCS Classification	Clayey Gravel (GC)					

Figure 6a: Atterberg Limit Results at 0.37m

Table 4a and figure 6a show the Atterberg limit test results for the disturbed soil sample at 0.37m depth for the strip foundation of the distressed building. The Unified Soil Classification System (USCS) revealed that Liquid Limit (LL) value was 16.1% and the Plasticity Index (PI) was 9.9% indicating that the soil was **GC** (clayey gravel) as the Atterberg limit was above the **A-line** and **PI > 7**. **According to** the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Official (AASHTO) classification system the disturbed soil was classified as **A-2-4 (silty or clayey gravel sand)** as **LL < 40** and **PI < 10**. **The result** suggested that the soil has a mix of gravel and fine-grained clay which would serve as a fairly good material for supporting the foundation but may have some cohesion due to the clay content, which could affect drainage and compaction.

Table 4b: Atterberg Limit Test Results at 0.9m depth

Depth:	0.90m							
Atterberg Limit Test								
Liquid Limit							Plastic Limit	
Number of Blows	50	39	30	26	19	12		
Can Number	M4	M3	H4	C4	C3	A8	K1	X4
Can Weight (g)	47.7	50.1	52.9	50.05	47.7	48.4	47.9	46.8
Can Weight + Wet Soil (g)	56	60.5	62.4	59	57.5	58.7	52.4	53.6

Can Weight + Dry Soil (g)	53.6	57.4	59.4	55.9	54.1	54.2	51.3	51.8
Weight of Water (g)	2.4	3.1	3	3.1	3.4	4.5	1.1	1.8
Weight of dry soil (g)	5.9	7.3	6.5	5.85	6.4	5.8	3.4	5
Moisture Content %	40.7	42.5	46.2	53	53.1	77.6	32.4	36
AASHTO Classification	A-7-5							
USCS Classification	MH (inorganic silt)							

Figure 6b: Atterberg Limit Graph at 0.9m

Table 4b and figure 6b show the Atterberg limit test results for the disturbed soil sample at 0.9m depth for the pad footing of the distressed building. According to the USCS classification, the LL value was 52.2% and the PI value 18% suggesting that the soil was **MH** (inorganic silt with high plasticity) as **LL ≥ 50** and **PI < 20** and Atterberg limits below the A-line of the plasticity chart. Based on AASTHO classification, the soil was classified as A-7-5 as LL > 41% and PI < 30% indicating the soil sample as clayey soil. The result indicated that the soil may be susceptible to volume changes with moisture fluctuations that may lead to settlement and swelling over time.

Dynamic Cone Penetration Test Result

Table 5: Dynamic Cone Penetration Test Result

MAPREF GEOTECHNICAL LTD

Dynamic Cone Penetration Test (DCP)

Field Record Sheet

PROJECT	STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY OF DISTRESSED BUILDING		
CLIENT	RESEARCHERS		
Blows/ Count	2/Count	2/Count	Date:16/07/2024
Test No	1	2	
Tested Depth	0.37-1.27m	0.9 -1.80m	
0	80	81	
1	160	157	
2	220	222	
3	265	290	
4	325	360	
5	400	420	
6	464	475	
7	524	548	
8	585	615	
9	650	685	
10	714	744	
11	780	805	
12	847	873	
13	920	960	

Table 6: Bearing Capacity Result

0.37-1.27m		0.90 - 1.80m	
Tested Depth (m)	UCS (Kn/m ²)	Tested Depth (m)	UCS (Kn/m ²)
0.37 - 0.47	51	0.90-1.00	53
0.47-0.77	64	1.00- 1.30	62
0.77-1.07	63	1.30-1.60	59
1.07-1.27	55	1.60-1.80	50
Disturbed Layer			

Table 5 showed the field readings obtained for the disturbed layers using the dynamic cone penetration apparatus at the depths for two blows per count. These penetration values were interpreted using Win DCP 5.0 software to obtain the bearing capacity of the soil as presented in Table 6. The DCP test results revealed that the soil was clayey with a low bearing capacity of 53 KN/m². This was due to the high moisture content of the soil that may lead to differential settlement (Eze et al, 2023)

Non Destructive Test (NDT) Results

The result of the non-destructive test conducted using the Schmidt rebound hammer apparatus were presented in table 7. The result revealed that the grade of concrete obtained was fair with an average compressive strength value of 20N/mm² (Ojedele et al., 2024).

Table 7: Non-Destructive Test Result

MAPREF GEOTECHNICAL LTD
CONCRETE INTEGRITY TEST
REBOUND HAMMER METHOD

PROJECT: STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY OF DISTRESSED BUILDING
LOCATION: UNWANA
CLIENT: RESEARCHERS
TESTED BY: MAPREF DATE: 16/06/2024

Table with 7 columns and 15 rows. Columns: Structure Ref., C001, C002, C003, and two empty columns. Rows include: Tested Member (Column), Hammer Position (A), Surface Condition (DRY), Age of Concrete (Days) (≥ 28), Rebound Number (1-10), Average RHR (28), Compressive Strength (N/mm2) (20), and Average Compressive Strength (N/mm2) (20).

LAB TECH. CONTRACTOR CONSULTANT ENGINEER REP

Conclusion

The following conclusions were made for the study;

1. The geotechnical test results revealed that the soil type at 0.37m depth was clayey gravel soil with 24.84% moisture content.
2. The geotechnical test results revealed that the soil type at 0.9m depth was clayey soil with low bearing capacity of 53KN/m² that caused distressed in the building under investigation.
3. The grade of concrete was fair with an average compressive strength 20N/mm² for the structural element of the distressed building.
4. The Investigations showed that the depth of the strip foundation and column base at 0.37m and 0.9m respectively were not adequate for the structure.

Recommendations

The soil conditions beneath the building foundation should be treated to improve the bearing capacity of the soil. Foundation repairs should be provided on the distressed portion of the building to enhance the lifespan of the structure.

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